

β -Phenylethanol Amines. Part II*. Studies on Cyclodehydration of a Few Acylamino Alcohols

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Cyclodehydration of some acylamino alcohols to their corresponding isoquinolines has been studied. *N*-[β -hydroxy- β -(3, 4-methylenedioxyphenyl)ethyl]-cinnamamide and its dihydro derivative yield readily the corresponding isoquinoline derivatives, viz., 1-(styryl)-6, 7-methylenedioxy- and 1-(β -phenyl)ethyl-6, 7-methylenedioxy-isoquinolines, whereas *N*-[β -hydroxy- β -(*p*-methoxyphenyl)ethyl]-cinnamamide and its dihydro derivative fail to cyclise when subjected to the Bischler-Napieralski reaction. During this reaction *N*-[β -hydroxy- β -(*p*-methoxyphenyl)ethyl]-cinnamamide suffers degradation to *trans*-cinnamamide and a dark brown styrene polymer.

In a previous communication (Adityachaudhury and Chatterjee, this *Journal*, 1959, 36, 585) a new method for the preparation of various β -phenylethanol amines and its extension in the syntheses of an acylamino alcohol, viz., aegeline, *dl-trans-N*-[β -hydroxy- β -(*p*-methoxyphenyl)ethyl]-cinnamamide, and an isoquinoline base, papaverine, has been described.

Since isoquinoline alkaloids are generally synthesised from acylamino derivatives of β -phenylethyl or ethanol amines, it was thought interesting to investigate whether (a) aegeline, *N*-[β -hydroxy- β -(*p*-methoxyphenyl)ethyl]-cinnamamide (I), (b) dihydroaegeline, *N*-[β -hydroxy- β -(*p*-methoxyphenyl)ethyl]-dihydrocinnamamide, and other two similar amides, viz., (c) *N*-[β -hydroxy- β -(3, 4-methylenedioxyphenyl)ethyl]-cinnamamide (II) and its dihydro derivative, (d) *N*-[β -hydroxy- β -(3, 4-methylenedioxyphenyl)ethyl]-dihydrocinnamamide, all having requisite acylamino structures, can be cyclised by the Bischler-Napieralski reaction to the corresponding isoquinolines. Studies on cyclodehydration of these amides are described in this communication. It seems pertinent to mention that the amides (c) and (d) have been synthesised for the first time by the present investigators.

N-[β -Hydroxy- β -(3, 4-methylenedioxyphenyl)ethyl]-cinnamamide (II) was prepared by the condensation of β -hydroxy- β -3, 4-methylenedioxyphenylethyl amine (Adityachaudhury and Chatterjee, *loc. cit.*) with cinnamoyl chloride. The amide crystallised from acetone in fine needles, m.p. 176-77°. The amide on hydrogenation with Adams' catalyst afforded *N*-[β -hydroxy- β -(3, 4-methylenedioxyphenyl)ethyl]-dihydrocinnamamide, m.p. 134-36°.

Cyclisation of the amide (II) with phosphorus oxychloride in dry toluene furnished 1-(styryl)-6,7-methylenedioxyisoquinoline (III) in fairly good yield. The base was obtained as an oil, which was converted into its picrate, m.p. 230-31° (decomp.). This isoquinoline base is not known in the literature. The picrate shows characteristic absorption maxima in the UV region at 252 (log ϵ , 4.01), 279 (log ϵ , 3.73), and 313 m μ (log ϵ , 3.64) in ethanol.

N-[β -Hydroxy- β -(3,4-methylenedioxyphenyl)ethyl]-dihydrocinnamamide, when cyclised over phosphorus oxychloride in dry toluene, afforded 1-(β -phenyl)ethyl-6,7-methylenedioxyisoquinoline (IV) in good yield. The base was purified by chromatography over Brockmann alumina, followed by crystallisation from methanol, in shining colorless rods, m.p. 83-85°. The base exhibits characteristic absorption maxima in the UV region at 238 (log ϵ , 4.72), 278 (log ϵ , 3.72), 316 (log ϵ , 3.62), and 329 m μ (log ϵ , 3.71) in ethanol. The hydrobromide of the base (IV) was crystallised from methanol in glistening needles, m.p. 253-54° (decomp.).

* Part I: This *Journal*, 1959, 36, 585.

(III): $R_3 = -CH=CH.Ph.$ (IV): $R_3 = -CH_2.CH_2.Ph.$

The extension of the above method of cyclisation in case of aegeline (I) and dihydroaegeline met with failure. Both these amides turned brown spontaneously when treated with phosphorus oxychloride and phosphorus pentoxide and yielded a dark brown resinous mass on heating for 10 to 15 minutes. The reaction products after being processed for the corresponding isoquinolines did not give positive tests with alkaloidal reagents, indicating the failure of ring closure. The neutral fraction from cyclodehydration products of aegeline yielded a compound, which crystallised from benzene in fine needles, m.p. 140-41° (yield 10%). The latter fits the formula C_9H_9ON . It was characterised as *trans*-cinnamamide. Formation of *trans*-cinnamamide during the cyclodehydration of aegeline obviously indicates that the other fragment of the alkaloid-amide is a styrene derivative. The latter, however, underwent a rapid polymerisation into a dark resinous mass. It might be recalled (McCoubrey and Mathieson, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1949, 696) that during cyclisation of the benzoyl derivatives of *m*- and *p*-nitrophenylethyl amines, considerable proportions of the corresponding *m*- and *p*-nitrophenyl cyanides were formed as byproducts. The reason for failure of cyclisation is possibly due to inductive deactivation of the methoxyl group in aegeline (I) and dihydroaegeline, *meta* to the point of ring closure. In fact, the amides derived from 2,4-dimethoxyphenylethyl amine and 2,4-dimethoxyphenylisopropyl amine fail to yield the corresponding 3,4 dihydroisoquinolines by the Bischler-Napieralski reaction (Govindachari and Lakshmikantham, *Proc. Ind. Acad. Sci.*, 1957, 46A, 414).

* EXPERIMENTAL

N-[β -Hydroxy- β -(3,4-methylenedioxyphenyl)ethyl]-cinnamamide.—An ethereal solution (20 c.c.) of cinnamoyl chloride (3 g.) was added dropwise to β -hydroxy-3,4-methylenedioxyphenylethyl amine (3 g.), prepared by a new method described previously (*loc. cit.*), and dissolved in the same solvent (30 c.c.) with constant shaking, when the amide was precipitated. A cold aqueous 10% solution of NaOH (30 c.c.) was added towards the end of the reaction. The amide was filtered, washed several times with water, and crystallised from acetone in fine needles (3.2 g.), m.p. 176-77°: (Found: C, 69.52; H, 5.39. $C_{19}H_{17}O_4N$ requires C, 69.43; H, 5.45%).

N-[β -Hydroxy- β -(3,4-methylenedioxyphenyl)ethyl]-dihydrocinnamamide.—The preceding amide (2 g.) on hydrogenation with Adams' catalyst (0.3 g.) for 2 hours in aldehyde-free ethanol (300 c.c.) showed an uptake of one mole of hydrogen. The solution was filtered and concentrated, when the desired amide was obtained. It was crystallised from acetone in glistening colorless needles (1.75 g.), m.p. 134-36°. (Found: C, 69.15; H, 6.26. $C_{18}H_{19}O_4N$ requires C, 69.00; H, 6.06%).

Dihydroaegeline.—Aegeline (2 g.) was hydrogenated with Adams' catalyst for 2 hours in aldehyde-free ethanol (250 c.c.), when it showed an uptake of one mole of hydrogen. Dihydroaegeline (1.8 g.) was crystallised from a mixture of ethanol and ethyl acetate in colorless plates, m.p. 140°. (Found: C, 72.34; H, 7.14. Calc. for $C_{18}H_{21}O_3N$: C, 72.24; H, 7.02%).

* All m.p.s. are uncorrected.

Cyclisation of N-[β-Hydroxy-β-(3,4-methylenedioxyphenyl)ethyl]-cinnamamide.—A solution of the amide (1.5 g.) in dry toluene (8 c.c.) and POCl₃ (7 c.c.) were refluxed at 110° for 2 hours. The reaction product was poured into crushed ice. The aqueous layer was separated and the toluene layer extracted with 4*N*-HCl (4 × 10 c.c.). The combined acid extract was washed with ether and the acidic aqueous solution was thoroughly cooled and basified with dilute NH₄OH solution. The liberated base was extracted with ether (3 × 50 c.c.), washed with water, dried over anhydrous potassium carbonate, and the solvent removed, when the desired 1-(styryl)-6,7-methylenedioxyisoquinoline was obtained as a pale yellow liquid (0.51 g.). The base was characterised as its picrate.

Picrate of 1-(styryl)-6,7-methylenedioxyisoquinoline was prepared by adding a saturated ethereal solution of picric acid (0.2 g. in 10 c.c.) to an ethereal solution of the base (0.2 g. in 5 c.c.). The resulting yellowish brown picrate was crystallised from methanol in fine, shining needles, m.p. 230-31° (decomp.). (Found : C, 57.42; H, 3.41; N, 11.31. C₂₄H₁₆O₆N₄ requires C, 57.14; H, 3.11; N, 11.11%).

Cyclisation of N-[β-Hydroxy-β-(3,4-methylenedioxyphenyl)ethyl]-dihydrocinnamamide.—A mixture of the amide (1.0 g.) in dry toluene (30 c.c.) and POCl₃ (6 c.c.) was refluxed at 110° for an hour. The solvent was removed in *vacuo* and the residue extracted with 4*N*-HCl (4 × 25 c.c.). The combined acid extract was well cooled and basified with an aqueous 10% solution of NaOH (75 c.c.). The liberated base was extracted with ether (6 × 50 c.c.); the extract (300 c.c.) was washed with water, dried over anhydrous sodium sulphate, and concentrated, when the base was obtained as a solid (0.65 g.). This synthetic base, 1-(β-phenyl)ethyl-6,7-methylenedioxyisoquinoline, was purified by chromatographic resolution over a column (6 cm × 1 cm) of Brockmann alumina using benzene as a developer. Fractions were collected in 15 c.c. portion, each (Table I).

TABLE I

Eluent.	Fractions.	Residue on evaporation.
Benzene	1-3	Oily residue
"	4-6	Colorless rods; m.p. 82-84°
"	7-8	Nil

Fractions 4-6 were crystallised from benzene in rods, m.p. 83-85°. (Found : C, 77.76; H, 5.56; N, 4.95. C₁₈H₁₆O₂N requires C, 77.97; H, 5.41; N, 5.05%).

Hydrobromide of 1-(β-phenyl)ethyl-6,7-methylenedioxyisoquinoline was prepared by dissolving the base (0.2 g.) in methanol (5 c.c.) and adding a few drops of aqueous hydrobromic acid (48%), when colorless, shining needles separated. These were crystallised from methanol, m.p. 252-53° (decomp.). (Found : N, 4.08. C₁₈H₁₆O₂N.HBr requires N, 3.9%).

Attempted Cyclisation of Aegeline.—A mixture of aegeline (1.0 g.), suspended in dry xylene (25 c.c.), and POCl₃ (5.0 g.) after being refluxed for 10 minutes was poured into crushed ice. After some time, the aqueous layer was separated and the xylene layer extracted with 4*N*-HCl (4 × 10 c.c.). The combined aqueous acid extract was shaken once with ether (50 c.c.) and made neutral with sodium bicarbonate, when a white solid separated. The latter was extracted with ether (4 × 25 c.c.). The ether extract (A) was washed with water, dried over anhydrous sodium sulphate, and the solvent removed. The aqueous solution was basified with NH₄OH solution and extracted with ether (3 × 25 c.c.). The ether extract (B) on evaporation left no residue.

The neutral compound, isolated from ether extract (A), was crystallised from benzene in shining needles (0.12 g.), m.p. 138-39°. It was further purified by chromatographic resolution over Brockmann alumina (5.0 g.) using the following as developers (Table II). Fractions were collected in 25 c.c. portion, each.

TABLE II

Eluents.	Fractions.	Residue on evaporation.
Petroleum ether (b.p. 60-80°)	1-3	Oily residue, not crystallisable.
Benzene	4-8	Colorless needles, m.p. 140-41°.
	9-11	Nil

Fractions 4-8 on recrystallisation from benzene furnished colorless needles, m.p. 140-41°. (Found : C, 73.54 ; H, 6.14 ; N, 9.49. Calc. for C_9H_9ON : C, 73.46 ; H, 6.12 ; N, 9.52%).

The neutral substance was found to be *trans*-cinnamamide from its analysis, and m.p. and mixed m.p. determinations with a synthetic sample of cinnamamide (*trans*).

Attempted Cyclisation of Dihydroaegeline.—Dihydroaegeline was subjected to cyclodehydration under the same experimental condition as described for aegeline. No alkaloidal material could be isolated from the reaction mixture.

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